

Complementary Results - Explainability Practices and Challenges from the Experience of a Brazilian Industrial Research and Innovation Company

1. PARTICIPANTS' QUOTATIONS

This section presents representative quotations from participants related to quality attributes, challenges, and cultural aspects associated with explainability.

Quality Attributes. Regarding quality attributes, participants often described explainability as an enabling means to achieve other desired qualities rather than as an end in itself. This perspective reflects a user-centered view of explainability, in which explanations are valued for their role in supporting users' comprehension and confidence in the system. The following quotations illustrate this perspective. Figure S2 summarizes the quality attributes that, according to the participants, can be achieved through explainability.

P07: Explainability requirements are fully related to quality attributes.

P09: I think that, in a way, it contributes a little to each one [*quality atributos*], you know? And in the end, it results in satisfaction. You convince the user. Comprehensibility comes from having more clarity. Security is about being able to trust what is being done. Transparency is understanding what is being done. Comprehensibility is closely related to satisfaction.

Fig. S1. Quality attribute can be achieved through explainability.

Challenges. The challenges of incorporating explainability into ML projects were varied. The following quotations illustrate the examples challenges mentioned by the participants.

P08 – To identify whether a project requires explainability—and, if so, to understand its importance—it is necessary to have clarity about what should be delivered as explainable. When there is a lack of understanding about what constitutes an explainability deliverable, the entire process becomes more complicated. This, in my view, is one of the main challenges.

P10 – There is a lack of understanding about what should be delivered as explainability, particularly within the project and development teams, rather than on the client side. This issue is not limited to developers, but is especially evident during requirements analysis. If explainability were clearly defined as a requirement, implementation would follow more naturally, as it would become a formal obligation. However, in many cases, even requirements analysts do not fully understand this aspect or ask the client whether it is important. Therefore, the core challenge lies in the lack of understanding of what explainability is, what should be delivered, and what it actually entails.

Fig. S2. Challenges to implementing explainability in ML projects

Cultural. Most interviewees agreed that explainability, when considered as a requirement, is strongly influenced by cultural aspects, as illustrated by the following quotations.

P13 – The answer is a very clear yes. We are adopting AI, and we see that people believe AI will solve all the problems in their lives, that it knows everything about everything. And that is not exactly what AI does.

P04 - I think that, if we consider cultural requirements, the issue here is indeed cultural: people do not understand what explainability is. Perhaps it is important to ask what level of knowledge the client has about explainability, because if they are not familiar with the concept, they are unlikely to request it.

P02 - If we divide users into two major groups, there are those who want to use the system without understanding it, simply for convenience and ease of use, and those who want to better understand what is happening behind the scenes. So yes, I believe this is still a cultural issue, especially because there are questions that not even specialists can fully answer, such as why one model performs better than another.

P01 - I believe it is cultural in the sense of a lack of understanding and lack of exposure. In many cases, this aspect is not even mentioned in the work plans we prepare. This actually represents an opportunity, for instance, to include explainability as part of the service offering and to foresee it explicitly in the project plan.